

Exploring the Applications of Natural Language Processing for Text Analysis: A Focus on Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract— Researchers have focused a lot of emphasis in the last 10 years on sentiment analysis, the automatic extraction of expressions of positive or negative sentiments from text. Regarding people, groups, locations, occasions, and ideas, they have both positive and negative attitudes. It is now possible to start extracting feelings from websites thanks to the tools given by natural language processing and machine learning as well as other methods to work with massive amounts of material. In this paper, we discuss some of the difficulties in sentiment extraction, some of the approaches that have been used to overcome these difficulties, and our approach that analyses sentiments from user feedbacks and produces results that go beyond just polarity but use those polarities in service profiling and quality. The approach can be improved based on promising results, which demonstrate that sentiment analysis in websites can be used to meet the needs of the business environment.

Keywords — Natural Language Processing (NLP), sentiment analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Processing(NLP) is a fast developing discipline with a lot of potential to address problems in the real world. NLP has attracted a lot of interest recently because of its capacity to improve website user experience. The potential of NLP to handle real-world issues in the construction sector by utilizing various NLP techniques is examined in this research. The suggested system seeks to provide an avant-garde and user-focused online construction management system. The report covers important NLP breakthroughs, such as sentiment analysis of NLP-based company reviews. The final objective is to demonstrate how NLP can revolutionize the virtual service experience and help users save time and make wise decisions. In conclusion, this work demonstrates the potential of NLP to change the construction management sector and provides insightful information for both scholars and practitioners.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In their study "Sentiment Analysis for e-Services," Fernando Santos-Sanchez and Andres Mendez-Vazquez [1] highlight the exponential growth of new e-services online every year. Many of them are required to analyse and interpret vast amounts of data. Many of them, nevertheless, fail to consider the feelings and attitudes expressed on the website when conducting their analyses. Consequently, in this work,

we proposed a novel method of obtaining relevant data from a Web search engine by examining the sentimental and emotional content of each page. This information can offer a fresh way to gauge how a product is being received by the public: It is easy to determine how the online community feels about the product based on the average sentimental rates in the forums, both good and negative. Additionally, by grouping the comparison pages for easy access, this classification enables the identification of the best sales options for a given product and greatly reduces the time required to find the best options. Therefore, we think that this system is the start of a new way to assist the user in choosing the best product to buy and makes it possible to have a better understanding of how the users perceive the suggested products.

In their study "Integrated Feedback Analysis And Moderation Platform Using Natural Language Processing by Ambarish Moharil, Shreya Singh, Yash Dravid, Harshal Dharap, and Prof. Vijaykumar Bhanuse[2], the authors explore sentiment analysis to ascertain the sentiment of the comments and reviews. The paper discusses the significance of preprocessing raw data, which includes actions like eliminating special characters and symbols, deleting stop words, stemming, and lemmatization, for machine learning classification and natural language processing. The study also explains the use of tokenization to vectorize a given text corpus and the use of two tokenizers, count vectorizer and TF-IDF tokenizer, to assess the sentiment of reviews and feedback. The study concludes by explaining how TF-IDF determines the term frequency and inverse frequency of terms and how the admin can view the TF-IDF score matrix for words with a threshold greater than 0.5 to summarize the entire review or feedback in two to three words rather than reading it altogether.

Kusrini, Mochamad Mashuri [3], in their paper "Sentiment Analysis In Twitter Using Lexicon Based and Polarity Multiplication" they discuss the use of sentiment analysis on Twitter data to determine the type of sentiment in tweets. The article highlights the importance of text mining and natural language processing techniques in analyzing the large amount of data generated on Twitter. The article also discusses the potential applications of sentiment analysis in various domains, such as product reviews, market research, and political elections. The study focuses on the use of

lexicons and multiplication polarity for sentiment analysis and suggests the need for further improvement in lexicon semantics to improve accuracy.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Pre-processing

The reviews from the dataset are first collected. As is common knowledge, processing a text is crucial before classifying it. In the second step, the dataset's pre-processing and redundant data cleanup are the main priorities. To ensure that writing conventions can be followed, standardization of punctuation is first carried out. Following that, all non-alphabetic characters from reviews, including numbers, emotion letters like smileys, punctuation marks like periods, hyphens, and apostrophes, are eliminated. The review's words are then all capitalized in lowercase. As a result, each divided word and phrase is employed in further processing. *Sentiment Tokenization*

The entire review text is tokenized in this stage by segmenting it into sentences (based on the use of periods) and then breaking each phrase down into words. Following the text's tokenization, the next step is frequently to perform a morph syntactic analysis to identify characteristics, such as its grammatical or lexical category. The term "POS tagging" refers to this study.

B. POS Tagger

A POS tagger is a linguistic technique used in natural language processing that takes as input text written in a specific language and assigns POS tags to each word in a phrase, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc. An adjective, a noun, a verb, a pronoun, an adverb, a preposition, a conjunction, and an interjection are examples of the eight POS in English. Stanford POS is the POS tagger used in this study. In addition to recognizing more intricate syntactic elements than simply eight, the tagger is able to provide 36 different tags. POS tags provide information about a word's in formativeness; as a result, they can be utilized to determine a term's score during the categorization process.

C. Negation

Negation reverses the polarity of currently paired words in a sentence. Negation words, like "not," "can't," and "don't," invert the polarity of the word they are used with. A negation word, for instance, will always become negative when it is combined with a positive word. On the other hand, when a negation word is combined with a negative word, it becomes positive. Therefore, in a sentiment classification, the negation words must be appropriately handled. The work done by Pang et al. was modified through this procedure.

D. Term Score

The review-related feature vector representing the POS is used in this method, which subsequently displays a number of emotion scores. The sentiment lexicon, the primary data source for the majority of SA approaches, is used to assign a term score to each sentiment-carrying word inside the input review. According to the "positive," "negative," and "neutral" notation of each sunset, SentiWordNet was established in this

study to set the sunsets as the major goal part of WordNet.

E. Sentiment Classification

The feature set that is used to display a user's opinion is what determines how sentiment is classified. Each review has a range of opinion words in a different order. Various grammatical words make up the chosen feature set. The unsupervised lexicon-based sentiment classification method is used in this work. The emotion categorization of review R is determined by the difference between the sums of its positive and negative phrase scores.

METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Pre-processing

The reviews from the dataset are gathered as part of the data preparation. As is common knowledge, it is crucial to process a text before classifying it. The pre-processing and cleansing of redundant data in the dataset takes up the majority of the second stage. First, standardization of punctuation is done to make sure that writing conventions can be followed. After that, each review has all non-alphabetic characters—such as numbers, emotion letters like smileys, punctuation marks like periods, hyphens, and apostrophes—removed. The review's entire vocabulary is then changed to lowercase letters. Each split word and phrase is then used for additional processing.

A. Sentiment Tokenization

The entire review text is tokenized in this stage by segmenting it into sentences (based on the use of periods) and then breaking each phrase down into words.

1. POS Tagger

A POS tagger is a linguistic technique used in natural language processing that takes as input text written in a specific language and assigns POS tags to each word in a phrase, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc. An adjective, a noun, a verb, a pronoun, an adverb, a preposition, a conjunction, and an interjection are examples of the eight POS in English. Stanford POS is the POS tagger used in this study.

2. Negation

A list of negation words is provided for a negation handling procedure, and each sentence in the review is examined for the presence of a negation word. A negation process is used if a negation word is discovered; it is viewed as a collection of negation words that are defined as follows.

3. Term Score

The review-related feature vector representing the POS is used in this method, which subsequently displays a number of emotion scores. The sentiment lexicon, the primary data source for the majority of SA approaches, is used to assign a term score to each sentiment-carrying word inside the input review.

B. Feature Selection

This research focuses on the feature extraction of various POS (adjectives, adverbs, verbs, and nouns). Each feature in the feature selection process is given a tokenized tag with a word score assigned to it. Then, each tag feature is picked out individually to compare how well each POS tag affects the sentiment polarity. As a new feature set, a combination of sets of the greatest POS tags is produced.

Sentiment Classification

Sentiment categorization is based on the feature set that is chosen to reflect a user's viewpoint. Every review contains a range of opinion words in a different order. Different grammatical words make up the chosen feature set. The unsupervised lexicon-based approach is used in this study for sentiment classification. The emotion classification of review R is determined by the total of its positive and negative phrase scores divided by the difference.

1. Dataset and Evaluation Matrices

The dataset was cleaned and prepped before being used. The HTML parser, for instance, removed HTML tags. Additionally, all numbers and punctuation marks were removed. On a dataset, experiments were performed. The experimental dataset is a benchmark dataset made up of many domains.

IV. RESULT

We compared our method to the lexicon-based classifier in order to assess how well our suggested strategies performed. The first baseline is based on the theory that the polarity of a text may be determined by adding the individual polarity values of each word or phrase that is used in the text, where each term is linked to numerical scores that indicate information about positive and negative sentiment. If the sum of the positive and negative word polarities is larger than zero, the overall text polarity is said to be positive. If not, the text is thought to have a negative overall polarity. The second baseline counts the quantity of positive and negative word scores to ascertain the polarity of a text's attitude. According to this method, the overall word polarity of the text is deemed positive if the number of positive word polarity exceeds the number of negative word polarity. If not, the text's overall polarity is deemed negative.

TABLE I. POSITIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

<i>Company Name</i>	<i>Polarity</i>
GMR	3
Hindustan	4
NCC	2
DREAM	3

TABLE II. NEGATIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

<i>Company Name</i>	<i>Polarity</i>
KINGS Construction	2

Builders	1
ARC	0

V. CONCLUSION

Recent years have seen a substantial increase in interest in Natural Language Processing (NLP) due to its effectiveness in resolving practical problems. The potential for NLP to improve the customer experience in online construction management is examined in this research by utilizing a variety of NLP techniques. The suggested system intends to create an avant-garde and user-centric solution for online construction management that can efficiently process and analyze business behavior. The paper addresses important NLP breakthroughs, such as sentiment analysis of NLP-based company reviews. The final objective is to demonstrate how NLP has the ability to revolutionize the virtual servicing experience, allowing users to save time and make educated decisions.

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